

Fatigue Analysis of CFRP Lap Joints With Thermal Effects

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ABSTRACT

Double lap joints made up from uni-directional and $\pm 45^\circ$ CFRP laminates were analysed for their fatigue behaviour by a finite element analysis. A fatigue criterion which is based on the interlaminar stresses was used. Initial thermal stresses resulting from the curing of the joint were also included in the analysis. The uni-directional joint was found to have its fatigue strength smaller than that from experiments. The uni-directional laminated joint with initial thermal stresses included was found to have better fatigue strength at large stress amplitude than that without the inclusion of initial thermal stresses. At large stress amplitudes, the $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joint with initial thermal stresses included was found to have lower fatigue strength than that of the joint without thermal effects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Joining of composite laminates is a popular fabrication process for composite structures. The geometry of these joints has given rise to complicated interlaminar stresses, especially at the joining region [1]. It has been mentioned in previous publications, e.g. [2], that a strip of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminate, when cured from the manufacturing temperature to the room temperature, can result in initial thermal stresses in the laminate. These stresses can be large, especially at the free edge region. For the present lap joint situation, when these initial thermal stresses are coupled with the mechanical stresses resulting from an applied load, the stresses around the overlap region in the joint are lowered or increased, depending upon the ply orientations in the laminated joint.

Under normal operating conditions laminated joints can be subjected to cyclic loading and the understanding of the fatigue behaviour of these joints is therefore necessary. The fatigue behaviour of uni-directional CFRP lap joints has been studied by experiments in [3]. A fatigue life prediction model has also been incorporated. Results have been presented in the form of *S-N* curves as similar to those of conventional materials. However, the prediction was not used for joints made from angle-ply laminates. Experiments are usually time consuming and expensive and it is desirable to have available a computational method which can predict the fatigue life of laminated joints. In [4], the fatigue behaviour of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ CFRP

laminated plates has been analysed using a finite element analysis. This paper extends the analysis in [4] for the analysis of laminated joints.

As a basis of the formulation, the fatigue data of a basic lamina along and transverse to the fibre direction as well as for the in-plane shear are taken either from results of past investigators or by estimation. At any point in the laminated joint, the stresses resulting from a loading case can be predicted by a finite element analysis similar to that described in previous publications [2, 5]. The fatigue behaviour of the joint under a tri-axial state of stresses is different from that of a uni-directional case. A fatigue criterion, which is similar to a failure criterion for anisotropic materials and thermal response of laminates, will be used. The fatigue criterion will predict, under the combined stresses at a point, the fatigue life in terms of the number of cycles to failure. This means that the criterion can predict failure locally. Conceptually each node in the finite element mesh will have their corresponding number of cycles to failure, N , at a certain applied load. Using the interlaminar stresses and the fatigue criterion to be defined later, N can be worked out at each node in the whole laminated joint. The minimum value of N for all nodes can be obtained and can then be taken as the number of cycles to failure, N_f , for the joint. The results of the present analysis on uni-directional laminated joint will be compared with the experimental values in [3].

It is not difficult to image that as a result of high stress concentration around the joining region, fatigue failure is expected to initiate around there. It was shown that initial thermal stresses were present in a laminate after the curing process [2]. In this paper, joints made up from uni-directional and $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ CFRP laminates will be used as examples. The initial thermal stresses resulting from the curing process will be included in the analysis. The non-linear analysis on the laminates will be based on a quasi-three-dimensional anisotropic finite element and an initial stress iteration method to tackle the problem of material non-linearity. The initial thermal stresses of a laminate are first obtained by noting that after curing the laminated joint is cooled from its curing temperature, at which it is stress-free, to the room temperature. Various axial stresses will then be applied to the laminated joint to obtain the interlaminar stresses and finally the numbers of cycles to failure.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE LAP JOINT

Figure 1 shows the top half of a balanced double lap joint symmetrical about the $z=0$ plane. The top $\pm\theta$ laminate is lap-joined to the middle $\mp\theta$ laminate. This lap joint will be referred as the $[\pm\theta/\mp\theta]_s$ joint. An external cyclic stress is applied to the left-hand end of the top $\pm\theta$ laminate and to the right-hand end of the middle $\mp\theta$ laminate. Due to symmetry, it was only necessary to analyse the top half of the double lap joint cross-section shown in Figure 1. The mesh shown in this figure was used for the analysis of the uni-directional and $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joints. In the present arrangement a resin rich layer was included at the bottom of the $\pm\theta$ laminate and the top of the $\mp\theta$ laminate. The same resin material was also used for the adhesive layer.

3 FORMULATION

A full analysis of this problem requires the use of a three-dimensional numerical technique such as the finite element method. However, since the thickness of the individual ply is very small compared with the length and width of the plate, an accurate analysis of such a problem will

involve an extremely large number of finite elements. In [6] and [7] linear and non-linear analyses have been carried out on a step-tapered laminated plate using a quasi-three-dimensional finite element and the number of finite element used has been kept to be small. For these analyses, it is required that the lay-up geometry be balanced about the $z=0$ plane. Also, it is assumed that the strain generated in the x -direction is constant.

Figure 1. The finite element mesh of the top half of the laminated joint

In [8], Lekhnitskii obtains expressions for the displacement components u , v , w which correspond to the stresses which depend only on y and z . These expressions can be simplified for symmetry about the $z=0$ plane. Furthermore, experiments have shown that for laminated $\pm\theta$ strips subjected to a uniform end load the v displacement component, away from the free edges, is not dependent upon x [9]. It seems reasonable to apply this same condition in the present case bearing in mind the restriction that the angle plies are balanced about the $z=0$ plane. As a result, the displacements u , v , and w can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= xC_3 + U(y, z) \\ v(y, z) &= V(y, z) \\ w(y, z) &= W(y, z) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

It is interesting to note that the strain component in the x -direction, ϵ_x is equal to C_3 . This shows that the x -wise direct strain is constant throughout the joint, away from the edges. From a physical view this would seem to be possible providing the dimension of the joint in the x -direction is large compared with the dimension in the y -direction.

The formulations of the quasi-three-dimensional finite element and the initial stress iteration method which are used in the present study can be found in [5]. The formulation to take into account of thermal stresses has also been given in [2]. The fatigue criteria of composite lamina have been compared by various authors and have been summarised in [10]. These criteria are not based on all stress components present in the joint and a different approach is therefore adopted here. With this approach a criterion is formulated by modifying the Tsai-Hill composite lamina yield criterion [11]. In the present formulation, we use functions X , Y , Z , Q , R and S , all are functions of N_f , so that X , Y and Z are the lamina peak stresses in the x , y and z directions and Q , R and S are the lamina shear stresses with respect to shear stress components σ_{yz} , σ_{zx} , and

σ_{xy} , respectively, all at N_f cycles of alternating applied stress. The relationship between X, Y, Z, Q, R, S and N_f are shown in Table 1. The fatigue criterion is therefore

$$f^2 = \frac{3}{2(F + G + H)} [F(\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + G(\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2 + H(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + 2L\sigma_{yz}^2 + 2M\sigma_{zx}^2 + 2N\sigma_{xy}^2] \tag{2}$$

where $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{zx}$, and σ_{xy} are stresses in the lamina.

Table 1 *S-N* relationships

<u>Lamina</u>								
X (MPa)	1494.4	1494.4	1938.5	1900.4	1856.8	1787.4	1660.8	1283.7
N (cycles)	0	1000	4000	10000	21380	45709	10000	613823
X (MPa)	1184.3	1142.1	1100.0	1068.6				
N (cycles)	10^6	2154435	4641588	10^7				
Y,Z (MPa)	72.32	72.32	37.37	34.152	33.047			
N (cycles)	0	10^2	10^5	10^6	10^7			
Q,R,S (MPa)	300.43	300.43	124.27	97.075	96.238			
N (cycles)	0	21	10^5	10^6	10^7			
<u>Resin</u>								
X,Y,Z (MPa)	769.2	769.2	397.45	363.22	351.45			
N (cycles)	0	100	10^5	10^6	10^7			
Q,R,S (MPa)	1099.2	1099.2	454.63	355.15	352.07			
N (cycles)	0	21	10^5	10^6	10^7			

It is worth noting that in Eqn (2), since X, Y, Z, Q, R and S all are functions of N_f , f depends on N_f . From the observation of the general behaviour of *S-N* curves, it follows that as N_f increases from a small value, f increases. When N_f is increased to a sufficiently large value so that $f = \bar{\sigma}$, fatigue failure occurs. In the present formulation, an iteration procedure is carried out to search for this value of N_f . At any point in the joint, the stresses can be obtained from the finite element analysis. Using Eqn (2) and the iteration procedure, the corresponding value of N_f at which fatigue failure occurs at that point in the joint can be obtained. For all nodal points in the joint, their corresponding values of N_f are iterated and the minimum value of N_f is then obtained, and is taken to be the number of cycles to failure for the laminate.

Fatigue data in the form of *S-N* curves were taken, or derived, from [10] and [12]. Discrete values along these *S-N* curves were found and they were tabulated in Table 1. In particular, the CFRP lamina longitudinal data were obtained from [12], and the lamina transverse and shear data as well as the resin data were derived from data in [10]. The lamina ultimate values of strains as well as the relationship between the thermal expansion and temperature in a CFRP lamina can be found in [5].

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this investigation the number of cycles to failure for the joints at various axial applied stresses were obtained. The drop in modulus due to temperature change as well as due to the fatigue effects in the present case was neglected. They are now presented in the following two sections. For each type of joint, thermal effects were also included to investigate for their behaviour at elevated temperatures.

In all analyses, non-linear iteration was carried out to incorporate the non-linear material behaviour of lamina and resin. The stress analysis results showed that the non-linear analyses provided a reduction in peak stresses. As the degree of material non-linearity in the lamina and the resin can be quite high, especially in the shear component of the resin, it is important to model the non-linearity accordingly.

4.1 THE UNI-DIRECTIONAL LAP JOINTS

Two joints of overlap length 12.7 mm were considered. For each joint two cases were analysed. For the first case, only mechanical applied load was considered for the fatigue analysis. For the second case, initial thermal stress effect was included such that the joint was considered to be stress-free at the curing temperature of 132 °C. When the joint was cooled to the room temperature of 20 °C, interlaminar initial thermal stresses were present in the joint [2]. Then on top of these initial thermal stresses a uniform stress was applied to the joint in the y-direction. The co-ordinate system is defined in Figure 1. At various applied stresses the corresponding numbers of cycles to failure for the joint were found as described before and the results are shown in Figure 2. Also plotted on the same figure are the experimental results from [3] for the uni-directional joint.

Figure 2. S-N curves of uni-directional lap joints

For both cases with and without initial thermal stresses, the present method predicted lower values of N_f at all levels of alternating stresses than those from experimental results in [3]. It is worth noting that in a normal experimental investigation, fatigue failure is defined as complete failure. In the present analysis initial failure is predicted. So it is natural that the current results gave lower values of N_f than those from the experiment in [3]. It should also be noted that the current prediction uses a finite element mesh that contains sharp LH and RH step corners (*see*

Figure 1), which are basically sharp notches and provide high stress concentrations around these step corners. It was explained earlier that the present fatigue criterion uses the interlaminar stresses for calculating the number of cycles to failure at nodes. As a result of the very high stresses around these step corners, early fatigue failure of the laminated joints was obtained.

In [6], a step-tapered laminated plate was found to have very high stress concentrations around the step corner when subjected to a axial stress. When a fillet of resin was included at the step position, the magnitudes of peak interlaminar stresses were reduced. In reality when a joint is made, the shape of the resin layer at the corner position will not be a very sharp corner. So in practice the level of interlaminar stresses will be lower than those in the present analysis, and consequently the fatigue life will also be longer. It is therefore not difficult to imagine that the fatigue life depends on the detailed shape of the step corners.

For both cases with and without initial thermal stresses, the minimum number of cycles occurred at a position near the RH step corner at the adhesive/adherend interface of the lower laminate. The step-tapered plates analysed in [6] and [7] showed that the interlaminar stresses at a similar position were the highest, indicating fatigue failure to initiate from this position when cyclic loading is applied. In [13], it was indicated that the σ_z 'peel' stress is large in lap joints and is generally responsible for joint failure. However, as will be discussed below, although the peel stress is a dominating stress component, other stress components also have their own contribution towards the fatigue failure.

It was mentioned earlier that initial thermal stresses were found as a result of the curing of the joint from about 132 °C to the room temperature of 20 °C. These initial thermal stresses were small in magnitudes in general but became large near the step corners. However, they were still small in magnitudes when compared with the mechanical stresses under the applied stress. So the initial thermal stresses may not be too significant to the fatigue life of the joint. As there are a total of six components of stresses, some of the initial thermal stresses are positive and some are negative. Under the application of a mechanical axial load only, the individual stress component can be of opposite sign to the corresponding initial thermal stress component. So, when a laminated joint is considered to have initial thermal stresses present, and in addition an axial load is applied, each overall stress component may have its magnitude reduced, instead of an overall increase in magnitude. Referring to Figure 2, it can be seen that the fatigue strength of the joint with initial thermal stresses included is better at large stress amplitude but worse at small stress amplitude than the corresponding strength in the case with mechanical applied load only. Also, the static strength of the joint with initial thermal stresses included is 30 MPa larger than that in the case with mechanical applied load only.

By considering a laminated joint to have undergone the stage of cooling from the curing temperature to the room temperature, and subsequently heating back to the same temperature at which curing takes place, the laminated should have no initial thermal stress present. So the case with mechanical applied load only can be considered as the situation when the laminated joint is subjected to the same temperature as the curing temperature. Although practically the joint will not be used at such an elevated temperature, this case can be used to illustrate the fatigue behaviour of the laminated joint at a high temperature. Since the number of cycles to failure for the above two cases were not too different, it follows that between the room temperature and the curing temperature the fatigue behaviour of this laminated joint will not be too different. Alternatively, if thermal cycling is considered, that is, temperature cycling only and without external applied force, thermal fatigue failure for this joint will be unlikely.

4.2 THE $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ LAP JOINTS

Similar to the uni-directional laminated joint, the two cases with and without thermal effects included were considered for the $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joint. The results of the two cases are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the $S-N$ curves for the two cases are nearly collinear at small stress amplitude. Similar to the uni-directional lap joint, for both cases with and without initial thermal stresses, the minimum number of cycles occurred at a position near the RH step corner at the adhesive/adherend interface of the lower laminate. However, unlike the uni-directional joint, the dominating stress component in this case is along the direction across the fibre.

Figure 3. $S-N$ curves of $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ lap joints

It is clearly seen that the initial thermal stresses did not have an effect in changing the fatigue behaviour of the laminate below a stress amplitude of about 70 MPa. However, the laminate was found to fail at an applied stress of 68 MPa.

As indicated above, the case without initial thermal stresses included can be taken as the case when the joint is subjected to the same temperature when curing takes place. It follows that the fatigue life of the $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joint at an elevated temperature is the same as that at room temperature.

The fatigue strength of the two types of joints in the present investigation can be compared by using the curves in Figures 2 and 3. It is clear that the fatigue strength of the uni-directional joint is better than that in the $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ one, with respect to the present loading pattern. However, the use of $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joint is usually preferred by designers because applied load on a joint can be multi-axial, for which this type of joint is usually capable of resisting.

5 CONCLUSION

Using the formulation for the fatigue analysis of anisotropic balance laminated joint, the fatigue behaviour of uni-directional and $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ lap joints were studied, based on the interlaminar stresses inside the joints. The analysis took into account the initial thermal stresses in the joint

resulting from the curing process. The fatigue strength obtained for the present uni-directional joint was smaller than that from the experiment of a past investigator. The uni-directional laminated joint with initial thermal stresses included was found to have better fatigue strength at large stress amplitude than that in the case without the inclusion of initial thermal stresses. The $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ laminated joint was found to have very close $S-N$ relationship for cases with and without the inclusion of initial thermal stresses at low stress amplitude. The effect of the initial thermal stresses on the $[\pm 45^\circ/\mp 45^\circ]_s$ joint was a reduction in static strength.

REFERENCES

1. R. D. Adams and V. Mallick, A method for the stress analysis of lap joints, *J. Adhesion* **38**, 197-217 (1992).
2. C. M. L. Wu, Non-linear thermal and mechanical analysis of edge effects in angle-ply laminates, *Computers & Structures* **35**, 705-17 (1990).
3. A. J. Kinloch and S. O. Osiyemi, Predicting the fatigue life of adhesively-bonded joints, *J. Adhesion* **43**, 79-90 (1993).
4. C. M. L. Wu, Thermal and mechanical fatigue analysis of CFRP laminates, *Composite Structures* **25**, 339-344 (1993).
5. C. M. L. Wu, Non-linear analysis of edge effects in angle-ply laminates, *Computers & Structures* **25**, 787-798 (1987).
6. C. M. L. Wu, Analysis of tapered (in steps) laminate plates under uniform in-plane load, *Composite Structures* **5**, 87-100 (1986).
7. C. M. L. Wu, Non-linear analysis of tapered (in steps) laminate plates under uniform in-plane load, *Composite Structures* **7**, 205-223 (1987).
8. S. G. Lekhnitskii, *Theory of elasticity of an anisotropic elastic body*, San Francisco, Holden-Day (1963).
9. R. B. Pipes and I. M. Daniel, Moire analysis of the interlaminar shear edge effect in laminated composite, *J. Comp. Mat.* **5**, 538-548 (1970).
10. H. T. Hahn, Fatigue behaviour and life prediction of composite laminates, *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (5th Conf.)*, ASTM STP 674, S. W. Tsai, ed., ASTM 383-417 (1979).
11. R. Hill, *The mathematical theory of plasticity*, Oxford University Press, London (1950).
12. I. K. Partridge, (ed), *Advanced Composites*, Elsevier Applied Science, London (1989).
13. R. D. Adams, Strength predictions for lap joints, especially with composite adherends - a review, *J. Adhesion* **30**, 219-242 (1989).